

INNOVATIVE METHODS OF SELF-STUDYING FOREIGN LANGUAGES THROUGH A MULTILINGUAL VISUAL DICTIONARY

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Language is the most direct connection to other cultures. Being able to communicate in another language exposes us to and fosters an appreciation for the traditions, arts, history of the people associated with that language. The many cognitive benefits of learning languages are undeniable. People who speak more than one language have improved memory, problem-solving and critical-thinking skills, enhanced concentration, ability to multitask, and better listening skills. Nowadays, Multilingualism has become more than just “important”. Knowing a foreign language has evolved to be extremely beneficial. On the other hand, learning a foreign language is tough and involves a lot of mental exercise. On the individual level, it improves personality and increases your sense of self-worth. Vocabulary is the foundation of language. It's the raw building blocks that we can use to express our thoughts and ideas, share information, understand others and grow personal relationships. As a result, we have the opportunity to understand the world from the perspective of another culture and gain a greater appreciation of human society in all its diversity. Therefore, the importance of second language learning is gain reinforced [1].

The importance of Visual dictionary. A visual dictionary is a dictionary that primarily uses pictures to illustrate the meaning of words. Visual dictionaries are often organized by themes, instead of being an alphabetical list of words. For each theme, an image is labeled with the correct word to identify each component of the item in question. Visual dictionaries can be monolingual or multilingual, providing the names of items in several languages. An index of all defined words is usually included to assist finding the correct illustration that defines the word. The Visual Dictionary is designed to help you find the right word at a glance. When you know what something looks like but not what it's called, or when you know the word but can't picture the object, The Visual Dictionary has the answer. In a quick look, you can match the word to the image [2].

Multilingual visual dictionary presents a large range of useful current vocabulary. The dictionary is divided thematically, includes 650 pages, 3 big chapters, 4 languages and covers most aspects of the everyday world in detail. You will also find additional words and phrases for conversational use and for extending your vocabulary. The Visual Dictionary is more than a reliable resource of meticulously labeled images-it innovates by combining dictionary-scale definitions with exceptional illustrations, making it the most complete dictionary. The Visual Dictionary is an indispensable visual reference that goes beyond object identification to answer questions about function, significance and purpose. Ideal for teachers, parents, writers, translators and students of all skill levels, it helps the user understand a phenomenon and quickly grasp the meaning of a term, the characteristics of an object or simply learn something new [3].

Multilingual visual dictionary mobile application for language learners is a versatile specialized application that makes learning foreign languages easy, designed with high quality and developed with modern innovative technologies. This smartphone application aims to encourage the student to learn to speak as soon as possible. Knowing the vocabulary, set

phrases, and grammar helps to keep a conversation going in no time. The program is mainly intended for learners of all ages and will help to memorize words in different languages permanently or in the long term. The process of learning a new word through the program is carried out by looking at a picture of the word, listening, reading the spelling of the word (transcription), giving an example of the word in a sentence, and testing it in writing and in a test. A word successfully tested at three different times and in three different places is considered learned or mastered by the learner [4].

This guidebook is created for everyone that explore ideas and nurture curiosity about the world we live in. Multilingual Visual Dictionary has been designed to give you easy access to the vocabulary you need. It is a valuable vocabulary building resource and language teaching tool that is perfect for work, school, university, self-study, travel or simply browsing. There is a Visual Dictionary for every age... for every need... for everyone. You can find words organized themes or individual objects. You can see thousands of highly realistic illustrations and detailed diagrams. You can discover a visual world of information of immense scope and depth, around major subject fields. This Visual Dictionary contains a rich, detailed vocabulary, carefully developed from systematic and comparative terminology research. Extreme care is taken to ensure the accuracy of every word. The perfect tool to carry around when learning a new language.

REFERENCES

- [1]. Alice Maclin, Reference Guide to English: Handbook of English as a second Language. 2001.
- [2]. Oxford Wordpower Dictionary. Oxford University Press, 2016.
- [3]. ELI Picture Dictionary Tecnostampa – Recanati 2007
- [4]. Joanna Turnbull, Diana Lea, Dilys Parkinson et al [Editors], Oxford Advanced Learner's Dictionary 8th edition. Electronic dictionary. Oxford University Press, 2010.